

CORD-MI study on cystic fibrosis (CF)

English translation of the description in the project register of the German Portal for Medical Research Data

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Project description

Cystic fibrosis, also known as cystic fibrosis, is a congenital metabolic disease. In those affected, the formation of various body fluids such as saliva, bronchial mucus or pancreatic secretions is impaired, making them more viscous than in healthy people. Among other things, this causes breathing problems and digestive disorders, as the viscous mucus blocks the small branches of the bronchial tubes and the ducts of internal organs. Cystic fibrosis cannot be cured. However, with early diagnosis and consistent treatment, the progression of the disease can be slowed down. In the past, those affected died in childhood and adolescence, but today they live much longer. As a result, women with CF are becoming increasingly pregnant, although this is associated with an increased risk for themselves and the child. Pregnant women should therefore be cared for in a specialized center during pregnancy and birth. The extent to which this recommendation is implemented in practice is to be investigated.

Project details

Project goals

The primary aim of the study is to determine the proportion of pregnant women with CF who attend specialist hospitals with a cystic fibrosis center for the ongoing treatment of their cystic fibrosis disease who also use these hospitals for delivery. The relevant guideline recommends delivery at locations with cystic fibrosis expertise. The study is being conducted to answer the following research questions based on retrospective health data:

- What is the proportion of pregnant women with CF who gave birth in a CF center between 2015 and 2019?
- How often do complications occur during pregnancy and childbirth?
- Which child outcomes can be observed?

Scientific background

Cystic fibrosis (CF) is a congenital multi-organ disease. It is caused by a defect in the so-called CFTR gene, which regulates salt and fluid transport through epithelial cells. CF is one of the rare diseases affecting around 8,000 patients in Germany. The incidence in newborns in Germany is 1:3,300 to 1:4,800 [1]. Significant improvements in health and life expectancy have been achieved in recent years. Previously predominantly a childhood disease, there are now more adults than children living with cystic fibrosis in Germany.

As a result, women with CF are becoming increasingly pregnant, but this is associated with an increased risk for the pregnant woman and the child [1]. It is therefore recommended that care during pregnancy and birth takes place in a specialized center. In Germany, around 50 pregnancies are expected per year. The German Cystic Fibrosis Registry is a good source of data, in which medical data from around 6,100 patients from 91 CF facilities have been documented for over 20 years (www.muko.info).

Literature

- Naehrig, S., Chao, C.-M., Naehrlich, L., 2017. cystic fibrosis. Dtsch Arztebl Int 114, 564-574. <https://doi.org/10.3238/arztebl.2017.0564>
- Edenborough, F.P., Borgo, G., Knoop, C., Lannefors, L., Mackenzie, W.E., Madge, S., Morton, A.M., Oxley, H.C., Touw, D.J., Benham, M., Johannesson, M., European Cystic Fibrosis Society, 2008. Guide-lines for the management of pregnancy in women with cystic fibrosis. J. Cyst. Fibros. 7 Suppl 1, S2-32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcf.2007.10.001>

Material and methods

In the case of cystic fibrosis, a case-based evaluation of the data of hospitalized women with CF in the period 2015-2022 is carried out. In a first step, the cases are identified at each location in which a birth (O80, O81 or O82) was coded in addition to the diagnosis of cystic fibrosis (E84.x).

Project result

17 locations participated in the data delivery in order to answer the research questions. Individual results are highlighted separately below. A comprehensive scientific analysis is currently underway. In total, 14 of the 17 locations stated that at least one delivery of a woman with CF took place at their location between 2015 and 2021. In total, between 86 and 110 deliveries were reported by the 17 sites, depending on whether the category "1 to 5" with one delivery each or five deliveries per site was assumed. CF and complications during pregnancy and/or birth: When looking at complications in CF patients during pregnancy and/or birth, it becomes clear that gestational diabetes occurs most frequently. The figure shows that the ICD code O24.4 for "diabetes mellitus occurring during pregnancy" was documented in 25 to 52 CF patients. This high prevalence was to be expected. Distribution of complications during pregnancy and / or childbirth in CF patients in the observation period 2015-2021, indicating the ICD code and possible range of values (minimum, maximum): Designations of the ICD-10-GM codes:

- Metabolic disorders
 - E84.* ... Cystic fibrosis
- Other diseases of the mother that are primarily associated with the pregnancy
 - Q24.4 ... Diabetes mellitus, occurring during pregnancy
- Complications during labor and delivery
 - O64.0 ... Obstructed labor due to incomplete rotation of the fetal head
 - O64.1 ... Obstructed labor due to breech presentation
 - O75.1 ... Dangerous condition during labor and delivery
 - O75.2 ... Fever during childbirth, not elsewhere classified

Verteilung von Komplikationen während der Schwangerschaft und / oder Geburt bei CF-Patientinnen

Figure 1: Distribution of complications during pregnancy and/or childbirth in CF patients in the observation period 2015-2021, indicating the ICD code and possible value range (minimum and maximum)

Data providers involved

- Charité - University Medicine Berlin
- Johann Wolfgang Goethe University Frankfurt am Main / University Hospital Frankfurt
- LMU Hospital
- Otto-von-Guericke University Magdeburg / University Hospital Magdeburg
- Philipps University Marburg / University Hospital Giessen / Marburg
- TU Dresden / University Hospital Carl Gustav Carus Dresden
- University of Münster / University Hospital Münster
- University Hospital Aachen
- University Hospital Erlangen
- Albrecht-Ludwig-University Freiburg / University Medical Center Freiburg
- Heidelberg University Hospital
- University Hospital Cologne
- University Hospital Regensburg
- University Hospital Tübingen
- Ulm University Hospital
- University Hospital Würzburg